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Assessing FAIR Data Support Needs Amongst Data Supporters in the ODISSEI Community

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Abstract

This report outlines the main results of a survey fielded by ODISSEI and DANS among data supporters in the Netherlands. The survey was launched at the end of 2021 and focused on assessing the needs of data stewards supporting researchers working with (quantitative) social science data. Results indicate that, despite the large amount of FAIR resources available online, there is a need for practical guidance on how to 'do FAIR' in the social sciences, and highlight various challenges in the domain of privacy, data anonymisation and GDPR-compliance. To overcome these challenges, ODISSEI and DANS aim to build a website focusing on practical guidance on FAIR implementation in the social sciences, establishing a 'FAIR help desk' for ad-hoc support, and organise networking activities to facilitate connections among data supporters working in the social sciences.

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Introduction

ODISSEI - Open Data Infrastructure for Social Sciences and Economic Innovations¹ - is the national infrastructure for social scientists in the Netherlands. ODISSEI brings together researchers with the necessary data, expertise and resources to conduct ground-breaking research and support the computational turn in social inquiry. Through the ODISSEI Hub - one of the four workstreams of the ODISSEI Roadmap project² - various community and educational activities are organised to support the research community in the use of tools and technology developed by ODISSEI. Moreover, ODISSEI wants to help research data supporters working with (quantitative) social science data towards Open Science and the implementation of the FAIR principles³.

ODISSEI has more than 40 members including most of the social science faculties of the Dutch universities. While ODISSEI brings together these different stakeholders, providing common services and advice, members also have established data management teams to support FAIR data and Open Sciences practices at their local institutes.

To provide ODISSEI-wide FAIR Data Support, a team has been established which consists of the ODISSEI Data Manager and two representatives from DANS - the Dutch national centre of expertise and repository for research data⁴. DANS is a member of ODISSEI, as well as a partner in the NWO Roadmap project awarded to ODISSEI in 2020. This FAIR Data Support team aims to compile a wealth of useful resources, as well as facilitating exchange between data stewards working with researchers in the field of social sciences to share experiences and useful resources.

This report discusses the results of a survey that was set out to connect with the local data stewards and data professionals working with (quantitative) social science data. The survey primarily targeted, but was not limited to, data professionals based at the ODISSEI member organisations. The survey aimed to learn more about the Research Data Management (RDM) and FAIR data practices already established by the local RDM support teams. It was also set out to identify what the challenges in relation to RDM are, and how tailored FAIR data support could be set up to overcome them.

¹ ODISSEI website: <https://odissei-data.nl/nl/> [accessed 15-02-2022]

² Information about the ODISSEI roadmap project: <https://odissei-data.nl/nl/odissei/roadmap/> [accessed 15-02-2022]

³ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* **3**, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

⁴ DANS website: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/> [accessed 21-03-2022]

The results of the survey will be used to tailor the activities of the ODISSEI team to support addressing the most prominent common challenges identified. Moreover, the results are made publicly available to inform the community and bridge to other initiatives that are concerned with the strengths and challenges of data stewardship in the social sciences and beyond.⁵

Methods and respondents

The survey was designed by ODISSEI and DANS, and piloted in November 2021 to collect feedback from data stewards and research support professionals. The survey was then launched in November 2021 via Google Forms, after excluding other platforms due to usage restrictions, and remained open until January 2022. The final version of the survey contained 16 questions and an open field at the end to provide any comments or feedback on the survey. A copy of the survey and the questions is listed in [Appendix A](#).

Dissemination of the survey happened through two reiterations: at first the survey was disseminated through mailing lists (DANS and ODISSEI mailing lists, news items), social media (e.g. LinkedIn, Twitter), and through the Slack channel of the Dutch Data Stewards Interest Group (DSIG)⁶. Then, in January 2022, the survey was distributed to data support professionals identified among the university partners of the ODISSEI infrastructure who were targeted with personalised emails to increase the response rate. Overall, 27 responses were collected (combining the answers of one participant who answered twice).

There are some disclaimers to be made before interpreting the results. Although we consider the number of respondents to be satisfying for our project needs, it should be noted that the results do not necessarily represent the entire community of research data professionals in the social sciences. We think, however, that some of the outcomes give useful insights to the challenges that data supporters encounter in their profession, at an international level and among different research fields.

⁵ The role and responsibilities of data stewards as well as how training and education can be more professionalised is discussed in this recent report by Jetten et al. (2021). Professionalising data stewardship in the Netherlands. Competences, training and education. Dutch roadmap towards national implementation of FAIR data stewardship. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4623713>.

⁶ DSIG group: <https://www.dtls.nl/about/community/interest-groups/data-stewards-interest-group/> [accessed April 13th 2022]

Results

Profession of survey participants

Most respondents identified themselves as data stewards, but the survey was also filled in by other professionals, including Data managers and (Data) consultants, as well as others⁷ such as researchers, lawyers, librarians, policymakers, advisors and projects' PIs (see Figure 1). This result indicates that "data steward" as a job title does not fully represent those professions that support researchers in the management of their research data. **In this report we hence use the term "data supporter", which better encompasses the functions and tasks reported in the survey.**

Figure 1: Position of respondents (N=27).

Research fields of survey participants

Most of the respondents work within the Social Sciences and/or Economics (Figure 2), which were our primary target audiences as these are the disciplines ODISSEI covers.

Six respondents out of the total twenty-seven do not work with any social science discipline, though they work in neighbouring fields such as Humanities, Law, and Architecture⁸, but also Medical Science. Interestingly, twelve respondents out of twenty-seven indicated that they work with more than one discipline, **showing that the profession of data supporter is often an interdisciplinary one.**

⁷ Other answers included: Data Representative, Lawyer, Librarian, Policymaker, Principal Investigator, Research Infrastructure Manager, Researcher, Advisor information management

⁸ The NWO domain Social Science and Humanities (SSH) covers law and architecture, alongside social sciences, economics and humanities.

Figure 2: Discipline of reference (N=27, multiple answers possible).

Research Data Management aspects covered by the participants' work

Data supporters were asked to indicate which aspects of Research Data Management (RDM) they cover in their work (see Question #5 in Appendix A), to gain a better understanding into the actual tasks a data supporter in the social sciences (and beyond) is concerned with (see Figure 3)⁹.

Figure 3: Coverage of RDM aspects (N = 27, multiple answers possible).

⁹ The eight proposed RDM aspects are loosely based on the research life cycle steps outlined in the CESSDA's Data Management Expert Guide, with the addition of Data analysis as a complement of Data processing.

Data management plan, data storage and *data protection* have been indicated by the majority of the respondents as aspects covered in their job activities (respectively by 23, 22 and 22 respondents). These are followed by *data publication* and *data cleaning & organisation*. Only one in five respondents provides support with *data analysis* issues, and around two in five also provide support in *data discovery* and *data processing*.

In a nutshell, **data supporters appear to be involved in the preparation of a research project (e.g. DMP) and in the aftermath (e.g. storage and protection)**, but not so much during the execution (e.g. data processing and analysis). In the open field of the 'Other' option, **respondents also mentioned *privacy issues* and *research integrity*** as important aspects of their work.

It should be noted that the ranking of the aspects is almost identical (and percentages are similar) when we only zoom in on data professionals working with (any of) the SSH disciplines.

Challenges in RDM practices

The survey also aimed to gauge the challenges associated with each RDM aspect. For this, an item battery was administered (see Question #6 in the Appendix) asking, for each RDM aspect, to indicate how challenging this aspect is (the option 'not among my responsibilities' was also included in case the data supporter was not tasked with that RDM aspect). In addition, two open-ended follow-up questions (see Question #7 and #8 in the Appendix) were included: one to indicate additional challenging RDM aspects, and one to elaborate on what makes RDM challenging.

Concerning the item battery, Figure 4 shows the percentage of respondents indicating each RDM aspect as somewhat or highly challenging, after excluding those who indicated that these RDM aspects were not their responsibility. *Implementation of Open Science principles, Data protection, FAIR and Anonymization* appear to be the most challenging aspects of RDM for the survey respondents. *Data storage*, which was indicated as one of the most common RDM aspects covered by data professionals, is only challenging for half of them. Only one in four data professionals reported *DMP* to be challenging. *Data analysis* is challenging for half of the respondents, however it is only included in the responsibilities of six of the interviewed data supporters.

Figure 4: percentage of respondents indicating each RDM aspect as somewhat or highly challenging (out of 'valid' cases indicated in the plot - hence excluding the ones indicating 'Not part of my responsibility')

Thanks to the open-ended questions, in which respondents were able to indicate additional challenges they encountered in their work as well as to elaborate on the problematic aspects they perceive for the RDM aspects they indicated as challenging, it is possible to better understand the challenges faced by data supporters.

- As indicated above, **the implementation of the Open Science and FAIR principles is perceived as challenging** by many respondents. In the open-ended answers respondents clarified that the interpretation of what a "good enough" application of these principles would be remains vague. As one of the respondents says: *"there is no baseline for when these criteria are met. You could always do more to improve these criteria"*.
- Another aspect that emerges clearly is the **difficulty and lack of consensus on how to anonymize data**. Disagreements on data anonymization rules emerge because different people from different disciplines can have different ideas on what "fully anonymized" means. Problems of anonymization are often discussed in combination with other issues, such as data publication and legal aspects, and therefore appear quite central among the RDM practices. As explained by a data steward, *"Researchers often think simply removing some direct identifiers fully anonymizes research data and can then publish the data, but this is of course not"*

true. It is very hard to fully anonymize data and it is also difficult to determine when this is the case - there can be a lot of disagreement on this"

- Some respondents expressed the need to improve **awareness of RDM**. Despite RDM practices having become a normal step in many academic circumstances (funding application, reporting etc...), some of the respondents report that raising awareness for RDM and FAIR data is (still) quite challenging. Many researchers still see RDM as too time-consuming and 'bureaucratic', and this hinders their cooperation. As exemplified in one of the answers: *"many of our researchers are reluctant to spend extra time on this, and having to comply with GDPR also prevents researchers from being more cooperative"*.

Website on FAIR resources

Figure 5: perceived usefulness of the website (N=27)

The last part of the survey assessed whether respondents would value a website providing resources on FAIR data and RDM. The respondents' evaluation of the usefulness of such a website was mixed (see Figure 5). Forty percent of the respondents find it very useful, and only one respondent (out of 27) indicated this not to be useful at all. The open question allowing respondents to clarify their answers indicated that many respondents felt that there is no need for extra resources because **a lot of resources on Open Science and FAIR principles are already available online**, through a variety of national and international channels. As reported by one respondent: *"there is (already) a vast amount of catalogues, collections etc. of such resources, so I am afraid an additional source to check is not the most useful. [...]"*

However, despite the wealth of available material, the survey highlights a need for guidance on **how to effectively use these materials, as well as a need for connecting and**

contextualising the existing resources. In the words of a respondent, *"It would maybe be better to connect the existing ones and make them more visible, i.e. improve in disseminating the existing material"*.

Diving into the desirable resources such as website should include, quantitative results (based on Question #11, see Appendix) indicate that all but one of the envisioned resources that could be on the website appear to be desirable to more than half of the respondents (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Desirable resources to be included in the web page (N = 27, multiple answers possible)

Combining these insights with the open answers enables a better understanding of what kind of resources and guidance on RDM are deemed desirable, and why. *Testimonials and interviews* appear to be the least desirable resource to be included; *FAIR case studies*, instead, are found desirable by almost 75% of the respondents which is in line with the fact that 'Implementation of FAIR principles' was deemed challenging by many respondents (see Figure 4). Also in the open answer, respondents indicated they would like **more specific information on the application of FAIR focusing on the social sciences**, e.g. FAIR applied to social data and/or qualitative data. One respondent also specified that when it comes to social sciences, "I" (Interoperability) and "R" (Reusability) are the most challenging aspects.

GDPR and sensitive data and *ethical issues with FAIR data* are indicated as the most desirable resources, aligning with the fact that 'Data protection' was also ranked among the most challenging RDM aspects (see Figure 4). Guidelines on **Research Ethics and Research Integrity** in the Social Sciences were also mentioned in the open-ended answers on other resources respondents would deem relevant.

There also seems to be **a need to collect information on technical aspects**, with *Technical implementation of FAIR* and *Tools for checking FAIRness* indicated as desirable by three in four respondents. Also in the open answers, respondents reiterated that tools or software for checking the FAIRness of research data would be appreciated. Among the technical aspects of FAIR, and also linked to the point above about the challenge of Interoperability, guidelines on **metadata standards** (e.g. DDI) used in the Social Sciences have been indicated as desirable resources to be included.

An additional layer emerged in the survey that directly tackles the role of data supporters themselves, who expressed the need for more training and ad-hoc support.

- **Training:** Providing training to data supporters and researchers is seen as very useful by the survey participants (~80% of them indicated it as desirable). In the words of a respondent, *"Providing training (especially on qualitative data management) to data supporters and researchers is very important. If possible, I would also like to see trainings/resources on how to systematically search for open data/secondary data"*.
- **Tailored support:** The desire for tailored support to data professionals when this is needed emerges strongly from the survey, as to underline the importance of the *practice* of RDM over the theoretical knowledge. As indicated by a respondent, *"It is about the application of these principles and not about the theory which is found on a webpage. A support system with "flying doctors" might work better"*. It was also suggested to use such a platform to inform data supporters about *updates* in RDM and training materials.

Main Takeaways

This report summarises the results of a survey carried out jointly as part of the ODISSEI Roadmap project to investigate the RDM practices and challenges faced by data support professionals in the social sciences (and beyond), in order to set up an appropriate FAIR support facility. Though the small and selected sample does not allow generalisations, a number of important insights have emerged.

First of all, there appears to be **a need for practical guidance on how to 'do FAIR'**, tailored support that answers specific questions and challenges arising within social sciences, and even a need for tools and software to check FAIRness. Although a website on FAIR resources is generally considered useful, access to general information is not deemed desirable, as there are already (too) many sources of information online. Nevertheless, data

support professionals are aware of the rapid changes occurring in the RDM field, and indicated the need to create **a space where to be informed about updates and newly emerging RDM practices**.

Among the RDM aspects, **data anonymization, data protection, and issues with sensitive data, privacy and GDPR are seen as particularly challenging**, as emerged in different parts of the report. These aspects are pivotal, as they encompass different aspects of a research project, starting with the data management plan and leading to the data publication opportunities.

Challenges are made more difficult by the reluctance of researchers, who often see FAIR and RDM practices as time-consuming and burdensome. In this context, data support professionals highlighted the need to **raise awareness among researchers**.

Finally, the work of data supporters appears to be often interdisciplinary, which makes it more difficult to establish consensus over RDM practices, and depends a lot on discipline-specific standards and knowledge. This requires **tailored support**, reiterating the idea that a general FAIR support website would not be deemed very useful, unless it had also an “ad-hoc” support component, as well as very applied examples on RDM, FAIR and Open Science practices.

Even if it was not explicitly mentioned by data supporters, we inferred that more **networking** would be useful. Providing tailored support and practical guidance on the application of FAIR is more effective when based on existing, executed research projects. In this context, sharing experiences and having opportunities to exchange ideas and best practices appears to be highly valuable.

Next steps and recommendations

Based on the results of the survey, ODISSEI and DANS plan to implement the following steps.

- The creation of a **webpage on examples and resources on how to ‘do FAIR’ applied to the social sciences**. Along the lines suggested above, rather than general resources, such a page should be focused on the challenges in implementing FAIR and Open Science principles when working with social data. To this end, the page will include references to checklists and best practices.

- The webpage will include a contact form to a “**Social sciences FAIR help desk**” which can be contacted to discuss specific FAIR challenges with experts working at ODISSEI (including the ODISSEI Social Data Science - SoDa¹⁰ team and the team of the PDI-SSH-funded project Building a FAIR Expertise Hub for the Social Sciences) and DANS.
- The organisation of **networking activities**, to increase the connections among data professionals working within the social sciences and economics domains. This should be done in alignment with existing (and successful) activities such as the Data Stewards Interest Group¹¹ to avoid a dispersion of useful resources, but should at the same time allow to carve out a space to discuss specific issues concerning the social sciences. Related to this, as a general recommendation, we want to highlight that writing personalised emails to potential respondents has been exceptionally useful, not only to increase the response rate but also to open the communication channel with some of the data professionals in ODISSEI-affiliated institutions, some of whom did not know about ODISSEI. For this reason, it is also important to organise **events** particularly targeted at research data supporters to raise awareness and knowledge about ODISSEI and how it can facilitate their work.

¹⁰ <https://odissei-data.nl/en/using-soda/> [accessed April 13th 2022]

¹¹ <https://www.dtls.nl/about/community/interest-groups/data-stewards-interest-group/> [accessed 13th of April 2022]

Appendix A: Questionnaire

ODISSEI Infrastructure Survey - FAIR Data Support

ODISSEI Infrastructure Survey - FAIR Data Support ODISSEI (Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations) is the national research infrastructure for the social sciences in the Netherlands. ODISSEI brings together researchers with the necessary data, expertise and resources to conduct ground breaking research and embrace the computational turn in social enquiry.

In collaboration with DANS-KNAW (<https://dans.knaw.nl>), ODISSEI (<https://odissei-data.nl>) wants to support research data supporters working with (quantitative) social science data toward Open Science (<https://www.openscience.nl/en/what-is-open-science>) and the implementation of the FAIR principles (<https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles>). We want to compile a wealth of useful resources to be used in the day to day work by data professionals. In addition, we want to facilitate exchange between data stewards working with researchers in the field of social sciences to share experiences and useful resources.

This survey aims to get in touch with data stewards and data professionals working with (quantitative) social science data to learn more about their Research Data Management and FAIR data practices. It wishes to discover what the challenges in relation to Research Data Management are, and how tailored FAIR Data Support could be set up to overcome them.

***Required**

1. By participating to this survey I accept the privacy policies of DANS (<https://bit.ly/3dttMJK>) * Tick all that apply.

- I agree and I understand that I can also opt out at any time.

Research Data Management Practices

A few questions about your position and the Research Data Management (RDM) and FAIR data practices at your Institute.

2. What is your affiliation? Please indicate your Institute/University and division/department. *

3. What is your position? * Mark only one oval.

- Research Support Officer
- Data Manager
- Data Steward
- Librarian
- Data Representative
- Other:

4. Which discipline do you work with? Select all that apply * *Tick all that apply.*

- Social Sciences
- Humanities
- Economics
- Law
- Medical Sciences
- Other:

5. Which of the following aspects of RDM do you cover in your work? Please note that from now on we refer to "research data supporter" as a more encompassing term for all the aforementioned positions. * *Tick all that apply.*

- Data management plan
- Data cleaning, organisation, documentation
- Data processing (Computing services)
- Data storage
- Data protection (safety, security, etc..)
- Data publication
- Data discovery
- Data analysis
- Other:

6. To what extent do you see the following aspects of RDM as challenges in your work as research data supporter? If the aspect does not fall into your area of work/responsibilities, please indicate so. *

	Not part of my responsibility	Not challenging	Somewhat challenging	Highly Challenging
Implementation of FAIR principles	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Implementation of Open Science principles	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data protection (e.g. GDPR, balancing national and international regulations, privacy issues)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Anonymization procedures	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data storage/archiving options	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Licensing options	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data management workflow(s)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data management plan	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data analysis	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

7. Is there any other challenging aspect you would like to add to the list?

8. For the RDM practices that you indicated as challenging, can you please give more details about the problematic aspects?

FAIR Data Support Resources

ODISSEI and DANS-KNAW are planning to set up a web page with resources related to FAIR Data and Research Data Management. The aim of this page is that of providing guidance and support material such as training material, guidelines or software to check the fairness of research data. We aim to provide these support resources for both research data supporters and researchers.

9. Do you think such a web page would be useful for you? On a scale from 1 (not at all) to 5 (very), how helpful would such a web page be? * *Mark only one oval.*

- 1 (not useful at all)
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5 (very useful)

10. Can you elaborate on your answer?

11. Which resources would you want to see included in such a web page? Select all that apply. * *Tick all that apply.*

- Introduction to FAIR data
- Training materials on FAIR data (for research data supporters and trainers)
- Tools for checking FAIRness of data
- Testimonials and Interviews with FAIR data experts
- FAIR data case studies
- Research Data Management
- Ethical issues with FAIR data
- Technical implementation of FAIR data (e.g. Persistent Identifiers)
- GDPR and sensitive data
- Open Science

12. Are there other resources not listed above that you would find useful to be included in such a web page?

13. Are you familiar with ODISSEI? * *Mark only one oval.*

- Very familiar
- Somewhat familiar
- Not at all familiar

14. If you are familiar with ODISSEI, can you tell us more about your experience with it?

15. Would you like to be updated about future training and networking events for data stewards that DANS-KNAW and ODISSEI organise? * *Mark only one oval.*

- Yes
- No

16. If you answered yes to the previous question, please add your email contact below

17. Room for any other comments or suggestions